

Derivatives of Aluminium with Mono-, Di- and Tri-ethanol Amines

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Reactions of aluminium isopropoxide with mono-, di-, and tri-ethanolamines have been studied in presence of benzene. Reactions of monoethanolamine and aluminium isopropoxide gave mono-, di-, and tri-derivatives by simple stoichiometric reactions. Aluminium isopropoxide (1 mole) and diethanolamine (1 mole) afford $\text{Al}(\text{dieth. am.})\text{OPr}^i$, whereas the reaction in the molar ratio of 2:3 yields $\text{Al}_2(\text{dieth. am.})_3$. An equimolecular mixture of aluminium isopropoxide and triethanolamine yields aluminium triethanolamine. Molecular weight determination of diethanolamine derivatives shows them to have molecular association of about 4, whereas aluminium triethanolamine exhibits a hexameric nature. A convenient method of alcohol interchange for preparing the corresponding derivatives with higher alkoxy groups has been described.

A considerable volume of work has been done on organic derivatives of aluminium and the technique of alcoholysis in presence of benzene has been used successfully in the preparation of higher alkoxides¹⁻² and β -diketonates³ of aluminium. Not much work appears to have been done on the derivatives of aluminium alkoxides with organic ligands containing nitrogen; the only relevant reference in the literature is the preparation of aluminium triethanolamine from a melt of aluminium isopropoxide and triethanolamine by Hein and Albert⁴. These authors described this derivative to have a molecular association of 8. In the present paper have been described the reactions of aluminium alkoxides with mono-, di-, and tri-ethanolamines.

The reactions of aluminium isopropoxide and monoethanolamine were found to proceed stoichiometrically in the following way:

Compounds (I) and (II) are sparingly soluble (about 3 and 1.4% respectively), whereas (III) is insoluble in benzene.

Two moles of isopropanol were replaced (equation iv) by the reaction of aluminium isopropoxide (1 mole) with diethanolamine (1 mole), whereas the reaction (equation v) in the molar ratio of 2:3 liberated all the 3 moles of the alcohol per aluminium atom and yielded di-aluminium tri-diethanolamine (V) in the form of a solution in benzene, from which a white crystalline solid was obtained.

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1. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 585.
2. Mehrotra, *ibid.*, 1954, 31, 85.
3. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1961, 39, 795.
4. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1952, 269, 67.

An equimolecular mixture of aluminium isopropoxide and triethanolamine in benzene gave aluminium triethanolaminate (eq. v) with liberation of all the three molecules of isopropanol as below:

Compound (IV) is readily soluble in benzene, whereas (V) and (VI) are soluble in benzene.

All the reactions were carried out in presence of benzene and the isopropanol produced was fractionated azeotropically. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the alcohol by an oxidative method. The products were isolated by removing the excess of benzene by filtration or distillation and drying under reduced pressure (0.1-2 mm) at 30-40°. Attempts to distil these compounds were unsuccessful, as these decomposed on being heated under reduced pressure.

In view of the interesting results obtained by us on molecular complexity of some aluminium glycolates⁵, it was considered of interest to study the molecular association of these compounds also. The molecular weight determinations of Al(dieth. am.)OPrⁱ and Al₂(dieth. am.)₃ showed them to have molecular association of the order of about 4, whereas aluminium triethanolaminate was found to have a molecular complexity of about 6. The reasons for the association may be ascribed similar to those of aluminium glycolates⁵. The results of molecular weight determinations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Compound.	Conc. range per 15 ml of benzene.	Molecular weight.	
			Found.	Calc.
1.	Al(dieth. am.)OPr ⁱ	0.1033—0.3066 g.	946	189
2.	Al ₂ (dieth. am.) ₃	0.0867—0.2705	1536	363
3.	Al(trieth. am.)	0.0710—0.2455	984	173

Further, the reactions of mono and di derivatives, prepared as above, with higher alcohols (e.g. Buⁿ, Bu^s, and Bu^t) were carried out, thus providing a convenient method for preparing the corresponding derivatives with higher alkoxy groups:

EXPERIMENTAL

Throughout the work, apparatus with 'Quickfit' interchangeable joints was used. Rigorous precautions were taken to exclude moisture. All fractionations were carried out in a column packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total-condensation variable take-off stillhead.

Aluminium isopropoxide was prepared as described by Mehrotra². Mono-, di- and tri-ethanolamines were of "Judex" laboratory reagent grade and were distilled before use. Benzene (B.D.H.) was dried over sodium wire and finally by azeotropic distillation with ethanol; butanols (*n*-, *sec*., and *tert*.) were dried by distilling over corresponding sodium alkoxides.

Aluminium was estimated as oxinate gravimetrically. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldhal's method. Isopropanol was estimated by oxidation with *N*-K₂Cr₂O₇ in 12.5% H₂SO₄⁶.

Molecular weights were determined in benzene using a modified Gallenkamp ebulliometer⁷.

Reactions between Aluminium Isopropoxide and Ethanolamine

(i) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:1.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (4.0 g.) was added to ethanolamine (1.19 g.), when a white suspension was obtained without evolution of any noticeable heat. Benzene (70 ml) was added and after refluxing for 2 hours under a column, isopropanol liberated was fractionated. During refluxing a white solid separated, which after distilling excess of benzene was dried under reduced pressure to give a white powder, sparingly soluble in benzene, m.p. 130°. Isopropanol in the azeotrope was found 1.2 g. (against 1.17 g.) required for 1 mole. (Found: Al, 13.4; N, 6.6. Al(eth. am.) (OPrⁱ)₂ requires Al, 13.17; N, 6.8%).

(ii) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:2.*—To ethanolamine (4.39 g.) in benzene (70 ml) was introduced aluminium isopropoxide (7.31 g.). On shaking a flocculent mass was obtained. The mixture was refluxed followed by fractionation of isopropanol-benzene azeotrope till about 30-40 ml of benzene along with a solid was left. The solid was filtered in a dry

6. Bradley and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

7. Mehrotra and Puri, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1961, 3, 247.

atmosphere and dried at 30-40°/1 mm to furnish a white powder (7.0 g.) which was negligibly soluble in benzene, m.p. 120°. Isopropanol liberated was found 4.2 g. (against 4.29 g.) calculated for 2 moles. [Found: Al, 13.6; N, 12.9. Al(eth. am.)₂OPrⁱ requires Al, 13.1; N, 13.5%].

(iii) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:3.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (3.8 g.) was admitted to ethanolamine (3.44 g.) and benzene (50 ml) was added, affording a white mass which was refluxed followed by dropwise fractionation of benzene-isopropanol azeotrope from 72° till the temperature of the distillate was steady at 80°. Pure benzene was collected in a separate flask, leaving a solid along with about 40 ml of benzene. The solid was filtered and then dried under reduced pressure to yield a white powder, insoluble in benzene, m.p. 90°. Isopropanol liberated in the reaction was estimated as 3.25 g. (against 3.35 g.) required for all the three moles (in aluminium isopropoxide taken). [Found: Al, 12.8; N, 19.5. Al(eth. am.)₃ requires Al, 13.0; N 20.2%].

Reactions between Aluminium Isopropoxide and Diethanolamine

(i) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:1.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (8.3 g.) was added to diethanolamine (4.28 g.) in benzene (80 ml) to form a solution. After refluxing and fractionating the alcohol liberated in the reaction, a small amount of the solution was left in the reaction flask which was evaporated under reduced pressure to furnish a crystalline solid, soluble in benzene. Total amount of isopropanol was found 4.77 g. (against 4.88 g.) required for 12 moles. [Found: Al, 13.9; N, 7.2. Al(dieth. am.)OPrⁱ requires Al, 14.2; N, 7.4%].

On distillation being attempted of the above compound, a residue was left at 280°/0.1 mm. (Found: Al, 16.7%).

(ii) *In the Molar Ratio of 2:3.*—Diethanolamine (2.1 g.) was transferred to aluminium isopropoxide (2.76 g.) in benzene (50 ml) to form a solution. After refluxing and fractionating the benzene-isopropanol azeotrope, a small amount of a solid along with 30-40 ml of benzene was left, which was dried under reduced pressure to give a white product, fairly soluble in benzene. Isopropanol liberated was found to be 2.4 g. (against 2.43 g.) required for all the 3 moles. [Found: Al, 14.4; N, 11.2. Al₂(dieth. am.)₃ requires Al, 14.8; N, 11.5%].

On distillation being tried, a residue was left at bath of 270°/0.01 mm. (Found: Al, 15.9%).

(iii) *In the Molar Ratio of 1:2.*—Aluminium isopropoxide (4.1 g.) was admitted to diethanolamine (4.2 g.) in benzene (70 ml). The isopropanol liberated in the reaction was fractionated azeotropically with benzene till the temperature of the distillate was steady at 80°. In the end a little solid residue along with benzene was left. The excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue dried at 35°/0.1 mm to yield a white solid (4.7 g.). Isopropanol found in the azeotrope was 3.5 g. (calc. for 3 moles in aluminium isopropoxide taken, 3.6 g.). [Found: Al, 11.7; N, 11.5. Al (dieth. am.)₂ requires Al, 11.5; N, 11.9%].

On distillation being attempted of the above compound, a liquid (diethanolamine) came at 120°/0.1 mm, indicating the disproportionation of the above compound.

Reaction of Aluminium Isopropoxide with Triethanolamine in Equimolecular Ratio

Aluminium isopropoxide (4.26 g.) was added to triethanolamine (3.1 g.) in benzene (70 ml). The solution was refluxed under a column followed by fractionation of isopropanol liberated in the reaction azeotropically with benzene. A little solid separated. In the end about 30 ml of benzene was left, from which crystallised a small amount of a solid slowly. The mother liquor was rejected and the solid dried under reduced pressure to yield a white solid, fairly soluble in benzene. Isopropanol liberated in the reaction was estimated as 3.69 g. (against 3.75 g. calculated for 3 moles). [Found: Al, 15.1; N, 7.8. Al(trieth. am.) requires Al, 15.6; N, 8.0%].

Alcohol-interchange Experiments

For alcohol-interchange experiments (summarised in Tables II, III, and IV), the general procedure was the same; a brief account is given in one instance only, viz., the reaction of aluminium mono-isopropoxy di-ethanolamine (1.9 g.) and butanolⁿ (0.74 g.). The reactants were mixed in benzene (40 ml). After refluxing for an hour under a fractionating column, the isopropanol produced in the reaction was fractionated azeotropically with benzene. Pure benzene was distilled till there was left a little solid along with benzene, which was dried under reduced pressure. [Found: Al, 12.7; N, 12.4. Al (eth. am.)₂OBUⁿ requires Al, 12.27; N, 12.7%].

TABLE II

Reactions of Al(eth. am.)₂(OPr)₂ with butanols.

Al(eth. am.) ₂ (OPr) ₂ .	Butanols.	Benzene.	Analyses*		M.P.
			%Al.	%N.	
2.20 g.	1.62g. (n)	50 g.	11.8	5.8	110°
1.56	1.17 (sec.)	40	11.9	5.7	130°
1.04	1.73 (tert.)	40	12.1	5.7	..

*Al(eth. am.)₂(OBU)₂ requires Al, 11.58; N, 6.0%.

TABLE III

Reactions between Al(eth. am.)₂OPrⁿ and butanols.

Al(eth. am.) ₂ OPr ⁿ .	Butanols.	Benzene.	Analyses*		M.P.
			%Al.	%N.	
1.90 g.	0.74 g. (n)	40 g.	12.7	12.4	80°
2.09	0.76 (sec.)	40	12.5	12.5	105°
1.76	1.61 (tert.)	40	11.8	12.6	110°

*Al(eth. am.)₂(OBU) requires Al, 12.27; N, 12.7%.

TABLE IV

Reactions of Al(dieth. am)OPri and butanols.

Al(dieth. am.) OPri.	Butanols.	Benzene.	A n a l y s e s.*		M.P.
			%Al.	%N.	
1.85 g.	1.10g. (n)	40 g.	13.5	6.8	135°
1.85	0.75 (sec.)	50	13.5	6.8	
1.59	2.51 (tert.)	50	13.1	6.7	

*Al(dieth. am.)(OBu) requires Al, 13.3; N, 6.9%.

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